

THE IMPACT OF WORK LIFE BALANCE IN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND PRODUCTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

There are many criticisms in free-market liberalism which argue that higher product-market competition and the "Anglo-Saxon" management practices it induces high productivity only at the expense of employees' work-life balance (WLB). The empirical basis of this issue is not clear. We found that WLB outcomes are significantly associated with better management, so that well run firms are both more productive and better for their employees. After controlling for management practices, however, we find no additional relationship between WLB and productivity. WLB practices are also not reduced by tougher competition, suggesting no deleterious effect of competition on employees' working environment. Finally, this paper examines the concept of relationship between the work life balance, management practices and productivity with Indian subsidiaries which adopt the superior management practices parent but the local family-friendly WLB practices.

INTRODUCTION

Work-life balance has emerged as a major theme during the last two decades, which witnessed a substantial intensification of work caused by economic uncertainty, organisational restructuring, and increase in business competition (Green, 2001; Millward et al., 2000). To respond to the new conditions, organizations demand higher performance and commitment from their employees, which is translated into expectations for working longer and for prioritizing work over personal life (e.g. see Perrons, 2003, pp. 68-72; Simpson, 2000; White et al., 2003). Indeed, recent survey data suggest that the pressure on employees to work longer hours under inflexible work leads to low productivity and least management practice.

ABOUT CONCEPTS-DEFINITIONS:

The phrase Work-life balance was coined in 1986 in the USA and until 1999 remained on the fringes of corporate usage and public dissemination. In 2000, Work-Life Balance has gone its usage. There has even been legislation enacted in many countries making Work-Life Balance crucial to the functioning of a corporation. All this translates into human resource department paying more and more attention to the aspirations of every employee and creating parameters of social interactivity to enable them to constantly discover their true potential. Work-Life balance boosts productivity by teaching people how to attain a higher level of achievements & enjoyment every day, both on and off the job. Critical drivers of performance, accountability and commitment are taught through the application of five easy to use tools. These tools produce immediate positive on and off the job results better individual management of project and relationship outcome

OBJECTIVES

- ✓ To Study the emerging issues in work life balance which influence the management practice and productivity
- ✓ To analyze the relationship between the work life balance and the management practice and productivity
- ✓ To suggest the various measure to improve the effective management practice and productivity of organization.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

- ✓ To improve the performance of the employees in future period high productivity and high sales
- ✓ To introduce the various innovative techniques to initialize the effective management practice.
- ✓ This study will help to analyze the attitude of the supervisor who is working with and for employee and delegating the work to their employees

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Human assets contribute much more than any other resources of an organization. When the human assets want to work efficiently and effectively, they should be motivated and trained in their job. Work-life balance of employees is important to every organization. Now most of the companies realize its importance and work for its improvement. Since a satisfied worker contribute more to the organization. Having a perfect work-life balance makes the employees to work with full fledge to achieve high productivity. The general purpose of this study is to analyze the work-life balance and to identify the needs of employees which improve the work-life balance of the employees in the company.

DATA COLLECTION:**Primary & Secondary data**

Primary data are original in character. The researcher himself collected the primary data by means of questionnaires in Villupuram- cuddalore districts co-operate milk producers` union limited (Aavin)-Villupuram". Relevant published and unpublished information like quality of work life, various management practice and details from company manuals listing the set of companies activities, and the company website.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Analysis to find the Relationship between the variables of work-life balance of the employees and productivity...

Hypothesis

H0: There is no Relationship between work-life balance of employees and productivity.

H1: There is Relationship between work-life balance of Employees and productivity

S.NO	LEVEL OF WORK LIFE BALANCE	ACHIEVING PRODUCTIVITY		Total	%	χ^2	df	Sig
		HIGH	LOW					
1.	HIGH	62	44	106	52.7%	16	1	3.841*
2.	LOW	39	55	94	47.3%			
Total		101	99	200	100			

INFERENCE:

The above table shows that there is 52.7% high work life balance leads to high productivity and 47.3% low work life balance leads to low productivity. The above said different of opinion is proved by using chi-square test. The Chi-Square value 16 is significant at 5 percent level. We have accepted the null hypothesis (Sig Value is 3.841).

So there is a significant difference between the variables work-life balance of employees and productivity achieved by an employee.

ANALYSIS OF MANAGEMENT PRACTICES THAT MAKES WORK-LIFE BALANCE HARDER:**TABLE: 2 CALCULATION OF WEIGHTED AVERAGE**

S. NO	FACTOR	W	MUCH HARDER	LITTLE HARDER	NO DIFFERENCE	NOT APPLICABLE	TOTAL	WEIGHTED VALUE
1	Deadlines and schedules	X1	56	24	12	8	100	3.28
		W1X1	224	72	24	8	328	
2	Type of work Do	X2	31	24	34	11	100	2.75
		W2X2	124	72	68	11	275	
3	No of hours you need to work	X3	23	29	34	14	100	2.61
		W3X3	92	87	68	14	261	
4	Additional work at home	X4	5	32	18	45	100	1.97
		W4X4	20	96	36	45	197	
5	Meeting Time training are scheduled	X5	38	23	24	15	100	2.84
		W5X5	152	69	48	15	284	
6	Starting and finishing time	X6	18	29	38	15	100	2.5
		W6X6	72	87	76	15	250	
7	Flexible timings	X7	42	22	24	12	100	2.52
		W7X7	126	66	48	12	252	

INFERENCE: From the weighted average method the above factors get ranked as below listed in table.

RESULTS FROM WEIGHTED AVERAGE METHOD

S. No	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Factor	Deadlines scheduling	Flexible timings	meeting/ training are scheduled	Type of work do	No. of hours need to work	Starting and finishing time	additional work at home
Weighted average value	3.28	2.94	2.84	2.76	2.61	2.5	1.97
Rank	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

From the above research (chi-square analysis) researcher can suggest that there is some relationship between the work-life balance of an employee and productivity. Mostly work life balance is directly proportional to the productivity of the organization. From the weighted average method of analysis researcher can suggest that management practices that make work-life balance harder are ranked below.

- Deadlines and schedules
- Flexible timings
- Times meeting/ training are scheduled
- Type of work do
- Number of hours need to work
- Starting and finishing times
- Having additional work at home.

The organization also needs to do some changes in work environments to identify their problem and at the same time need to take necessary measures which is relevant for our organization environment. The organization has to revise the management policies and practices and implement the effective management practices to improve the work life balance among the employees.

CONCLUSION

Work-life balance policies can assist employees achieving a balance between their work and personal commitments that is right for them. The policies need to be supported by the workplace culture, which reflects the beliefs, values and norms of the whole of the organization from the CEO to staff members. Other important factors in the success of work life balance policies include proper communication of commitment to the policies to existing and future employees, raising awareness of the policies, education of managers about the importance of policies, and training of managers on 'how to' implement these policies. This paper suggested friendly management practices which will provide feel free environment to the employees to improve the productivity which is the ultimate goal of any business.

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